

EPB TBM Foam Generation

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INTRODUCTION

Soil conditioning is often critical to high performance earth pressure balance (EPB) tunnel boring machine (TBM) tunneling. The injection of foam into the cutterhead tool gap and the subsequent mechanical mixing with scraped soil in the tool gap, cutterhead openings and in the excavation chamber, serves to transform the formation soil into a low permeability, low shear strength, compressible chamber material for steady face support and muck extraction. A significant body of research and literature exists on conditioned soil behavior, primarily based on laboratory studies (e.g., Vinai et al. 2007, Bezuijen et al. 2012, Budach and Thewes 2015, Williamson et al. 1999, Mori et al. 2016). However, very few if any published studies have focused on how foam is mechanically produced on board the TBM, what foam generation system characteristics are important, and how in-situ conditions such as ground pressure influence foam generation and system design. The lack of documented studies in the literature leaves many contractors ‘foaming in the dark’. The first part of this paper presents an overview of on-board foam generating systems for EPB TBMs, discussing the desired foam properties and quantities, how they are estimated, and key system parameters that deliver and influence these properties. The second part of the paper presents the results of foam generation testing in a laboratory-simulated EPB TBM soil conditioning system, focusing on the influence of a number of key parameters such as pressure, air velocity, generator fillings, elbows, etc. on foam properties.

TBM FOAM GENERATOR

Plumbing and Geometry

While all TBMs are somewhat different in terms of size and configuration of systems, we present here a reasonable layout and geometry of a foam generation system for a 6.5-7.0 m diameter metro-size EPB TBM. Figure 1 presents a general layout of a foam generation system, including the main components and plumbing. Foam generation begins with compressed air tanks, surfactant and polymer containers and diluted surfactant and polymer tanks. Surfactants are the key ingredient to generating foam. Various polymers are sometimes used to bind or disperse soil and may be included directly in the foam liquid line prior to the foam generator or added to the foam transport line after the foam has been generated. Air and foaming solution flow separately and are metered at prescribed flow rates needed to achieve the desired foam injection ratio and foam expansion ratio, both of which are described below.

The compressed air and foaming solution flow lines merge immediately upstream of the foam generator unit (sometimes called the foam gun). Foam generators can vary in diameter and length, and often include fillings such as beads, tubes, or steel wool to create an environment that promotes foam bubble generation. The foam created in the generator exits and travels to a rotary fluid joint at the rear of the excavation chamber, i.e., the bulkhead wall. The foam flows through the rotary fluid joint in dedicated channels and then flows to dedicated cutterhead ports.

For a metro-size EPB TBM, there are generally 4-7 ports at the cutterhead face that deliver foam to the soil in the tool gap. The number of ports grows with TBM diameter. There are often additional ports in the excavation chamber and in the screw conveyor. Each cutterhead port has a one-way valve to allow foam flow when desired and to prevent pressurized groundwater and soil from flowing into the foam pipes. When foam is to be delivered through a desired port, the foam pressure exceeds that of the formation water. This pressure differential opens the valve and allows foam flow. There are a variety of valve configurations used to accomplish this.

Figure 1 is labeled with pressures p , volumetric flow rates Q , and velocities v at various critical points that will be discussed throughout the paper. An important aspect of foam generation is the pressure distribution along the system, bookended by the compressed air pressure p_{comp} and the formation groundwater pressure p_w . The pressure systematically decreases as the air, foaming solution and ultimately foam travel downstream.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic of a generalized foam generation system in a TBM and (b) photo of a metro-size EPB TBM cutterhead

Foam Delivery

Two governing foam parameters are the foam expansion ratio FER and the foam injection ratio FIR . The FER is the volumetric ratio and/or volumetric flow ratio of foam to foaming solution (Eq. 1). The FIR is the volumetric ratio and/or volumetric flow ratio of foam to excavated soil (Eq. 2). The volumetric flow rate of excavated soil can be represented by the product of advance rate (AR) and excavated area (A_{exc}). FIR is conventionally expressed as a percentage.

$$FER = FER_p = FER(p = p_w) = \frac{Q_{foam}}{Q_{sol.}} \quad (1)$$

$$FIR = FIR_p = FIR(p = p_w) = \frac{Q_{foam}}{Q_{exc.}} = \frac{Q_{foam}}{A_{exc.} \cdot AR} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The appropriate total FIR , i.e., the sum of foam delivered through all ports, can vary with soil and groundwater conditions. Generally, the FIR varies from 20-70% (EFNARC 2005). FER values can vary

from 5-20 depending on soil types and groundwater conditions, e.g., the desire for a wet foam and less air introduced or a dry foam. While seldom clear during reporting, these FIR and FER values are generally calculated and reported at the pressure they are delivered into, e.g., p_w for cutterhead injection, p_{exc} for excavation chamber injection, and p_{sc} for screw conveyor injection. For simplicity here, we will focus on the most critical and common foam injection – through the cutterhead. Because the groundwater pressure is not measured on the TBM, the excavation chamber pressure p_{exc} , most often at springline, is used as a proxy for p_w . A subscript p is sometimes used (FER_p , FIR_p) to clearly indicate that these values reflect the in-situ pressure.

The delivery of air and foaming solution typically begins with a pressure-corrected calculation. Assuming cutterhead injection and using p_{exc} as a proxy for p_w , the desired foam flow rate \bar{Q}_{foam} (designated with a top line to reflect desired vs. actual Q_{foam}) is determined via equation (3) where D_{chd} is the cutterhead diameter. Note that the desired FIR remains constant and \bar{Q}_{foam} varies with advance rate AR .

$$\bar{Q}_{foam} = \frac{FIR}{100} \cdot Q_{exc.} = \frac{FIR}{100} \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} D_{chd}^2 \cdot AR \quad (3)$$

The corresponding desired \bar{Q}_{air} and \bar{Q}_{sol} are presented in equation (4). As shown in Figure 1, \bar{Q}_{air} reflects the flow rate delivered by a servo-controlled air mass flow controller (MFC). Using the ideal gas law and assuming constant fluid temperature throughout the foam generation system, the MFC flow rate is pressure corrected to deliver the desired flow rate at the cutterhead. Because $p_{air} > p_{exc}$, Equation (4) shows that the desired MFC air flow rate is lower than that desired at the cutterhead. The foaming solution flow rate need not be corrected for pressure as it is incompressible.

$$\bar{Q}_{foam} = \bar{Q}_{air} \frac{p_{air}}{p_{exc}} + \bar{Q}_{sol}. \quad (4)$$

Finally, the ratio of provided \bar{Q}_{air} and \bar{Q}_{sol} are determined by the desired FER per Equation 1.

Foam Flow Mechanics

Foam generation can be described as the vigorous mixing of two immiscible fluids (in this case air and liquid) to form a multiphase mixture in which tightly packed air bubbles are separated by thin liquid films called lamella. In TBMs, foam is generated by flowing air and a liquid water-surfactant solution through a pipe filled with porous media, such as randomly packed beads, steel wool, or perforated tubes. Two mechanisms of bubble creation within porous media are snap-off and lamella division (Ransohoff and Radke 1988, Radke et al. 1994) as shown in Figure 2. Snap-off (panel a) occurs when a bubble divides into one or more smaller bubbles as it is squeezed by a constriction. Lamella division occurs when a bubble ruptures as it flows through a branch point in the porous media, as in panel (b).

Our experiments also show that foam can be generated in the absence of porous media by simply flowing the liquid and gas through a pipe. In this case, bubbles likely form due to shear stresses and fluid mixing due to turbulence. These mechanisms likely play a role when foam is generated within porous media as well, particularly at high flow rates associated with turbulence. Consequently, one objective of our study is to vary the porous media and flow rates within the generator to investigate the competing roles of pore geometry versus fluid mixing. A better understanding of these mechanisms

could allow one to tailor the porous media and flow rates to deliver foams with desired properties, and even vary foam properties dynamically to respond to varying soil conditions and operating pressures.

**Figure 2. Foam bubble generation mechanisms in porous media:
(a) Snap-off and (b) Lamella division (after Ransohoff and Radke, 1988)**

Considering the TBM foam generation system, the key pressures, volumetric flow rates and velocities along five key cross-sections (*a - f*) are shown in Figure 3. The desired and delivered foam flow rate is pressure driven, and significant pressure losses exist along the system. At the upstream end, the pressure losses within the pipes carrying single phase air and liquid are generally negligible compared to those incurred downstream, even for cases where the single phases must travel tens of meters from their source containers. The air and liquid merge at the generator or immediately upstream of the generator and flow through the porous media (beads, steel wool, tubes) in a multi-phase fashion. Significant energy loss occurs, often greater than 2 bar, during multiphase flow through this porous media as foam is created. Upon exiting the generator, foam flow also induces significant pressure losses as it is delivered through the pipe joining the generator to the cutter head. When foam is generated in the rear of a TBM, such pipes are often on the order of ten meters long.

Foam is a complicated fluid that is both compressible and non-Newtonian with an effective viscosity that is typically orders-of-magnitude larger than that of water (Sibree 1933, Grove 1951, Wenzel 1967, David 1969, Wenzel 1970). Due to this large viscosity, foam flow through pipes is characterized by much larger pressure drops than for single phase flows or non-foam multiphase flows.

Understanding the source of pressure losses within foam generators is further complicated by the presence of the porous material. For single phase flows through porous media, such as pure water, pressure losses are well described by Darcy's law for low flow rates, and the Forchheimer equation for high flow rates (Joseph et al. 1982, Lage 1998). These equations show that pressure losses occur due to viscous effects in the small pore spaces, and additional inertial effects as the flow winds through tortuous pore paths. In the case of multiphase flow of air and water (without surfactant), additional pressure losses occur due to capillary effects and the fact that each phase must compete for the available pore space. Finally, in the case of foams, the restriction of the liquid phase to thin films lead to additional complicated flow phenomena that are not fully understood. As in pipes, foam flows through porous media are characterized by much larger pressure gradients than for comparable single-phase flows or non-foam multiphase flows. Considering these pressure losses, and that foam flow is pressure driven, it is important to design a foam generation system that has sufficient supply pressures – $p_{comp.}$ and $p_{sol.}$. Naturally, with consideration to Figure 3, $p_{comp.} > p_{air}^a > p_{foam}^b > p_{foam}^d > p_{foam}^f > p_w$.

Figure 3. Flow parameters and plumbing dimensions of a foam generation system on a TBM

The pressure at a given location in a foam generation system is primarily set by the downstream conditions. Consequently, pressure variations within the system are best understood by beginning at the cutterhead and working upstream. The analysis begins at the cutterhead where the pressure p_w is determined by the depth below the groundwater table. Working upstream, the pressure at the outlet of the foam generator can be expressed as p_w plus the pressure drop required to deliver foam from the generator to the cutterhead. Similarly, the pressure at the inlet of the foam generator can be determined by adding the pressure drop across the generator. Accordingly, with knowledge of the geometry of the foam generation system, e.g., pipe lengths, etc., one can estimate pressure losses and then determine the desired p_{air} and necessary p_{comp} . The primary difficulty is predicting the pressure drops across the generator and the pipe conveying foam to the cutterhead. A major objective of this study is to identify the various sources of pressure loss within TBM foam generation systems and develop simple practical relationships to predict pressure variations a-priori.

While the mass flow rates of air \dot{m}_{air} , solution \dot{m}_{sol} , and foam $\dot{m}_{air} + \dot{m}_{sol}$, are set by the mass flow controllers, quantifying the pressures p , volumetric flow rates Q , and flow velocities v , is complicated by the porous media, multiphase flow, and air compressibility. For the single-phase flows of air and solution upstream of the generator (location *a*), the velocities are computed per equation (5), where A is the cross-sectional area of the respective pipe, and ρ is the mass density (e.g., kg/m^3) of the air or solution.

$$v_{air}^a = \frac{Q_{air}^a}{A} = \frac{\dot{m}_{air}}{\rho_{air}^a A} \quad v_{sol}^a = \frac{Q_{sol}^a}{A} = \frac{\dot{m}_{sol}}{\rho_{sol}^a A} \quad (5)$$

Within the foam generator (location *c*), the cross sectional area is reduced by the presence of fillings and there is uncertainty as to whether the liquid and air travel with different velocities and pressures. We take the pressure measured at the inlet and outlet of the foam generator to be characteristic of both the liquid and gas, e.g., $p_{sol}^b = p_{air}^b$, and we estimate the pressure at location *c* as $p^c = (p^b + p^d)/2$. Following the convention for multiphase flow through porous media (Bear 1972), we compute separate superficial velocities for the air v_{air}^c , and liquid v_{sol}^c , as in equation 5, where A is taken to be the cross sectional area of the pipe containing the porous media. Though the liquid solution is

considered incompressible, the local air density is computed from the local pressure using the ideal gas law. As a result, the volumetric flow rate Q_{air} and velocity v_{air} increase considerably across the generator due to the downstream pressure loss. With the formation of tightly packed bubbles separated by thin liquid lamella, there is uncertainty as to whether the two phases in a foam actually flow with different velocities. Consequently, we also compute an effective foam flow rate $Q_{foam}^c = Q_{air}^c + Q_{sol}^c$ and a superficial foam velocity $v_{foam}^c = Q_{foam}^c / A$. Finally, we characterize the volumetric flow rate and velocity at the inlet and outlet of the foam transport tube joining the foam generator to the pressure chamber using an identical procedure, where A is then set to the cross sectional area of the tube.

EXAMINING THE CHARACTERISTICS OF FOAM

Foam generation principles were examined through careful laboratory testing with a foam generation system scaled appropriately from field conditions. The following sections describe the experimental setup, results and findings.

Experimental Setup

The scaled down foam generation system is shown in Figure 4. Compressed air and foaming solution are metered via mass flow controllers similar to a TBM system. Typical TBM supply pressures were duplicated, and in fact expanded to examine influence. Pipe diameters were scaled down because field volumetric flow rates are too high for laboratory testing. However, great care was taken to simulate the range of air and foam flow velocities observed on TBMs. Velocity is the important parameter because flow regime and energy loss is velocity-dependent and not volumetric flow dependent. We employ a variety of foam generator sizes in the experimental setup generator fillings, including 1 and 3 mm beads, steel wool, and perforated tubes.

A foam bubble capture device and digital microscope is used immediately downstream of the foam generator to capture and image the foam. This allows the detailed analysis of bubble size and bubble size distribution. A pressure chamber is used to mimic the pressurized environment that foam is deposited into in a tunneling environment, whether the formation water in front of the cutterhead or the excavation chamber. During foam generation in the laboratory, the chamber pressure is set and held constant at levels from 1-5 bar (absolute pressure).

Figure 4. Schematic of laboratory foam generation system and foam testing devices (pressure chamber and foam capture device) and laboratory foam generators with different filling materials. Not to scale.

Pressure and Velocity

A series of foam generation experiments was performed with the system shown in Figure 4. Three different excavation chamber pressures were simulated – 1, 2 and 3 bar (absolute pressures, i.e., 1 bar = atmospheric pressure). At each chamber pressure, the air flow velocity v_{air}^a was varied over 4-5 different values for each p_{ch} . This created a matrix of 14 experiments. For this series of 14 experiments, the foam generator was 200 mm in length and 25 mm in diameter. 3 mm beads were used for filling material. The foam transport pipe length from the exit point of the generator to the chamber was 1.0 m long and 6 mm internal diameter, exactly the same diameter as the air and solution supply lines. The foaming solution included a commercial surfactant with 5% concentration. The *FER* was fixed at 15, and according with equation 1, was calculated using each chamber pressure.

Figure 5 shows the pressure regime throughout the system for three experiments with a consistent average generator superficial air velocity ($v_{air}^c = 0.5$ m/s) yet at different values of p_{ch} . The chamber pressure p_{ch} is prescribed and held constant through the use of a pressure relief valve. Figure 5 illustrates that the pressure drop through the 200 mm long generator ($p_{foam}^b - p_{foam}^d$) and through the 1 m long foam transport pipe ($p_{foam}^d - p_{ch}$) are significant. The pressure drop across the generator was on the order of 1-2 bar and the pressure drop along the exit pipe (from the generator to the chamber) was 2-2.8 bar/m of pipe.

Figure 6 shows the pressure loss across the generator and along the 1.0 m long, 6 mm diameter foam transport pipe for all 14 experiments as a function of v_{air}^c in Figure 6a and average foam transport

velocity v_{foam}^e in Figure 6b. As expected, pressure loss increases with these respective velocities. The pressure loss also increases with chamber pressure.

Figure 5: (a) Absolute pressure levels and (b) pressure drops across the system for $v_{air}^c = 0.5$ m/s, 25 mm diameter, 20 cm long foam generator and 6 mm diameter, 1 m long foam transport pipe.

Figure 6: Pressure drops across the (a) foam generator and (b) foam transport pipe for 0.5 m/s average superficial generator air velocity, 25 mm diameter, 20 cm long foam generator and 6 mm diameter, 1 m long foam transport pipe.

The pressure loss in the foam transport pipe varies with foam transport pipe diameter. Three internal pipe diameters – 6, 9 and 12 mm – were investigated (keeping all other system parameters the same). Figure 7a illustrates the pressure loss measured along 1 m of the transport pipe as a function of v_{foam}^e . What is evident from Figure 7a is that transport pipe pressure loss is strongly influenced by foam velocity and somewhat influence by chamber pressure. Figure 7b presents the same data in an interesting way. Each of the three pipe diameters are delivering generally the same Q_{foam}^e albeit using much different velocities. Figure 7b shows the benefit of larger diameter in reducing pressure loss.

Figure 7: Pressure drop along the 1 m long foam transport pipe versus (a) v_{foam}^e and (b) Q_{foam}^e as a function of foam transport pipe diameter (6, 9, 12 mm) and chamber pressure (1, 3 bar). In all cases, foam generator is 25 mm diameter, 20 cm long, and beads are 3 mm.

Foam Behavior

For each of the 14 experiments described earlier, foam was captured, imaged and analyzed to characterize bubble size. The foam was captured immediately downstream of the foam generator as illustrated in Figure 4. A backpressure regulator was used to maintain the bubble capture device pressure equal to p_{foam}^d . This bubble capture process is described elsewhere (Mooney et al. 2016). While bubble characteristics are best reflected by a bubble size distribution histogram, a simplified mean bubble diameter is shown in Figure 8a as a function of p_{ch} and v_{air}^c . Figure 8a shows that both air velocity and chamber pressure have a significant influence on bubble size. Some additional results in Figure 8b show the influence of generator bead size on foam bubble size. Smaller beads have smaller pore sizes that leads to smaller bubbles through the snap-off and lamella mechanisms described earlier.

Figure 8: (a) Average bubble diameter measured at the generator outlet as a function of v_{air}^c for different chamber pressures (3mm beads, 20 cm length foam generator, 1m long, 6 mm diameter foam transport pipe); (b) average bubble diameter as a function of bead diameter ($p_{ch} = 1$ bar)

The engineering behavior of foam can be addressed by examining its stability and compressibility (or stiffness). Stability and compressibility were investigated using the pressurized chamber (Figure 4). Stability is typically measured by recording the drainage of liquid with time (EFNARC 2005). Compressibility is measured by recording the volume change due to a unit increase in pressure. Resilience in the context of foam behavior is measured by recording the recoverable deformation after five cycles of 1 bar pressure loading and unloading.

Figure 9 presents the liquid volume loss measured 30 minutes after foam generation at various air flow velocities and in the three chamber pressures. The air velocity has a small influence on stability in that higher velocities lead to more stable foam. The chamber pressure, on the other hand, has a significant influence on stability. Foams generated and deposited into higher pressure environments experience significantly greater stability. While not shown here due to paper length limitation, the reason for the increased stability has to do with smaller and more uniform bubble size at higher pressure. Smaller and more uniform bubbles are more stable and do not break down as quickly as larger and varied bubble sizes.

Figure 10 presents the compressibility measured by cycling the chamber pressure by 1 bar. The measured data points are accompanied by the theoretical compressibility of air for comparison. Figure 10 shows that the measured response matches theoretical air compressibility almost perfectly. The results also show that bubble size does not influence compressibility. The theory is that smaller bubbles have a greater internal pressure than larger bubbles, and therefore would be less compressible. This would manifest itself as a function of air velocity but these results show no influence of air velocity. It turns out that the difference in inner pressure between the bubble sizes we have observed is on the order of single kPa and therefore negligible compared to the 100, 300 and 500 kPa chamber pressures.

Figure 9: Foam liquid volume loss after 30 minutes as a function of v_{air}^c in three different chamber pressures

Figure 10: Foam compressibility at time = 5 mins for various range of flow rates at different chamber pressure using 3mm beads, 200mm length of foam gun and 1m-exit tube

Influence of Valves

Careful attention should be paid to cutterhead foam port valves and any valves where there is a significant reduction in cross-sectional area and corresponding increase in flow velocity. Such a rapid increase in velocity can cause cavitation that can destroy foam. The literature shows that foam can be severely degraded by flow through constrictions (Calvert 1988). The influence of the valve closing angle was investigated by physical simulation of a TBM valve in the laboratory. A ball valve is placed on the bleed-off line in the laboratory foam generation system (Figure 4). When the valve is completely open, foam flows through the bleed-off valve with good quality (i.e., uniform foam bubbles and consistent foam flow). However, when the valve is closed to some degree, considerably bigger bubbles are observed in the foam, the generated foam does not exhibit consistent flow and one can hear the air separation from the foam. To characterize this behavior, a series of tests was performed with four different valve opening angles, and the pressures along the foam generation system were monitored, particularly the pressure before the foam generator (p_{foam}^b), the foam pressure immediately after the foam generator (p_{foam}^d), and the pressure immediately upstream of the ball valve (p_{valve}). The test initiated with foam generation and flow using a fully opened valve (valve opening area is 100%). Pressures were measured and the ball valve was then closed gradually and in increments until poor foam quality appears as described above. The test results are shown in Figure 11. Foam exhibited good quality with the valve opening areas of 100%, 41%, and 30%. When the valve opening area reaches 22%, large foam bubbles were observed and foam flow was not consistent (air-liquid separation occurred). The valve pressure (p_{valve}) and foam pressure (p_{foam}^d) increase noticeably when the valve opening area decreases from 30% to 22% as shown in Figure 11. The most likely explanation for the poor foam quality is cavitation through the valve. Cavitation causes large vapor bubbles flowing downstream and air-liquid separation.

Figure 11. The influence of the exit valve opening area on pressures along the foam generation system

CONCLUSIONS

Foam generation on EPB TBMs is a complex process of compressible multiphase flow through a highly energy dissipative system. The pressure loss through typical foam generation lines is significant due to losses through the generator and through the foam transport line. Turbulent mixing and viscosity are key contributors to this. These pressure losses are velocity-dependent and foam transport pipe diameter-dependent. The air supply pressure required to overcome pressure losses and deliver foam into a formation water environment must be determined and delivered, otherwise foam velocity and flow rates will not meet the project needs. Foam bubble size and engineering properties (liquid loss with time, compressibility) are influenced considerably by pressure and flow velocity. Higher pressure and flow velocity produce foam with smaller, more uniform bubbles that have greater stability insofar as liquid drainage time.

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